

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A STUDY OF QUALITY TRAITS OF DUCK AND GOOSE EGGS SELECTED FROM DIFFERENT AREAS OF OYO METROPOLIS, SOUTHERN GUINEA ZONE OF NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

A study of quality traits of duck and goose eggs selected from different areas of Oyo metropolis, Southern Guinea Zone of Nigeria was investigated. A total number of 480 eggs (240 each of duck and goose eggs) were used for the study and 20 each of the species eggs were taken for measurement on weekly bases. Data were obtained on quality traits such as egg weight (g), egg length (mm), egg width (mm), shell weight (g), shell thickness, yolk weight (g), yolk length (mm), yolk height (mm), yolk circumference (mm), yolk index, albumen weight (g), albumen height (mm), albumen index and haugh unit. Significant ($P < 0.05$) effect was observed between the quality traits measured and the eggs from duck and goose. Duck eggs were better for egg weight (70.45g), egg length (62.34mm), shell weight (7.80g), shell thickness (0.49) and shell index (67.35) than the goose eggs. Most of the internal quality traits were also in favoured of ducks eggs for yolk weight (30.50g), yolk length (54.88mm), yolk circumference (6.66mm), yolk index (33.89), albumen index (7.89) and haugh unit (73.24) than the goose eggs while only albumen height was better for goose eggs of value 4.49mm. It can be concluded that there are significant variability in most of quality traits observed which favoured the duck eggs than eggs from goose.

Keywords: *Quality traits, eggs, duck, goose, southern guinea savanna*

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INTRODUCTION

Egg is known as one of most important components of human diet. There are many types of poultry species' eggs consumable as a protein and amino acid supplement (Polat *et al* 2013). According to recent statistical data (FaoStat, 2011), a total world production of chicken eggs amounts to about 1220 billion per year yielded mainly by chickens but also coming from other poultry species as 86 billion eggs per year.

Quality traits of eggs determine prices directly in commercial flocks and in egg processing enterprises, the weight of egg shell, albumen and yolk that form the egg as well as their compositions affect the amount and price of the product (Altan *et al* 1998). Egg weight is a parameter which could be determined about the egg without breaking the egg (Farooq *et al* 2001b). The composition of the egg varies among species. The size of the egg varies within population and to a lesser extent within clutches of birds. The egg traits such as egg weight, egg width, albumen and yolk are very important in poultry production due to their influence on egg quality and grading (Farooq *et al* 2001a), reproductive fitness of the chicken and embryonic development (Onagbesan *et al* 2007). The egg internal quality traits such as albumen weight and yolk weight are very important from nutritional and cholesterol content for human consumption (Spark, 2006).

In Nigeria, more emphasis is laid on domestic fowl to the neglect of other classes of poultry such as duck and goose eggs, smaller eggs such as quail eggs and the largest bird eggs, from ostriches (Adeyeye, 2012). The population of ducks in Nigeria was put at approximately eleven million (11,000,000) and reported to be distributed all over the agro- ecological zones of the country (Dariusz *et al* 2002). Domestic ducks and goose were ranked third among various poultry species in Northern part of Nigeria (Hassan and Mohammed, 2003). Ducks produce eggs of larger sizes and more nutritious than chicken, containing higher proportions of protein and dry matter (Etuk *et al* 2012). In comparison with chicken, geese play a minor role in production of meat and egg. In spite of this positive score, very little attention has been paid to the quality of meat and eggs, genetic improvement as well as improved husbandry practices to raise the performance of the domestic duck and goose. Therefore, the aim of the study was to evaluate the quality traits of external and internal variables of duck and goose eggs found around Oyo town, Southern guinea savanna zone, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Experimental site.

The study was carried out at the Agricultural Education Laboratory Unit of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo. Oyo State. Oyo lies on the longitude 3° 7' East of Greenwich meridian and Latitude 7° 5' North of the equator. It is about 5 kilometers north-eastward from Ibadan the capital of Oyo state. The altitude is between 300 and 600 meters above sea level. The mean annual temperature and rainfall are 27°C and 1247mm respectively (Amao *et al* 2013). This vegetation is southern guinea savanna zone of Nigeria.

Eggs used

Freshly laid eggs of duck and goose were obtained from some backyard rearers. Twenty eggs were obtained from each species weekly for twelve weeks and totaling two hundred and forty eggs for each species. These fresh eggs are used to evaluate the external and internal egg quality traits.

Collection of Data

The traits that were investigated on weekly bases are; Egg weight (g), Egg length (mm), Egg width (mm), Shell weight (g), Shell thickness (mm), Shell index, Yolk weight (g), Yolk height (mm), Yolk length (mm), Yolk circumference (mm), Yolk index, Albumen height (mm), Albumen index(mm), Albumen weight(g) and Haugh unit using the procedures of Kul and Seker (2004).

Statistical analysis

The data collected were subjected to General linear model analysis of variance procedure of SAS (2003), and means was separated using Duncan procedure of same software. The data were analyzed using the model specified below:

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + T_i + e_{ij}$$

Where, Y_{ij} = individual observation on eggs

μ = Overall mean

T_i = Fixed effect of i^{th} eggs (1, 2)

e_{ij} = Residual random error

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the least square means of external quality traits of duck and goose eggs. There are significant ($P < 0.05$) effect between the traits measured and the eggs of duck and goose. Egg weight, shell weight, shell thickness and shell index of values (70.49g, 7.80g, 0.49mm and 67.35 respectively were higher for duck eggs than the eggs from goose. No significant ($P < 0.05$) difference was obtained for egg length and egg width for both duck and goose eggs. The least square means of internal quality traits of duck and goose eggs was presented in table 2. Significant ($P < 0.05$) effect was observed between the internal traits measured and the eggs of duck and goose. Duck eggs were higher in values for yolk weight (30.50g), yolk length (54.88mm), yolk circumference (6.66mm), yolk index (33.89), albumen weight (28.78g), albumen index (7.89) and haugh unit than the values obtained for goose eggs while the albumen height was only higher for goose eggs of value 4.44mm than 4.99mm documented for duck eggs. No significant ($P < 0.05$) effect obtained for yolk height of the both eggs.

DISCUSSION

The present results indicated that the variables measured on both eggs of duck and goose are breed dependent. The values obtained for most of the traits were higher for duck than goose eggs. This kind of observations was in harmony with the noticed of Nayak and Mohanty, (2013) on physico-

Table1: The least square means of external quality traits of duck and goose eggs

Traits	N	Eggs	
		Duck	Goose
Egg weight(g)	240	70.45±1.47 ^a	63.49±1.82 ^b
Egg length(mm)	240	62.34±2.48	61.99±1.29
	240	39.40±0.99	40.22±0.79
Egg width (mm)	240	7.80±0.03 ^a	6.20±0.02 ^b
	240	0.49±0.02 ^a	0.42±0.01 ^b
Shell weight(g)	240	67.35±1.88	68.49±1.49
Shell thickness(mm)			
Shell index			

^{ab} Means along the same row with different superscripts are significantly (P< 0.05) different.

Table 2: The least square means of internal quality traits of duck and goose eggs

Traits	N	Eggs	
		Duck	Goose
Yolk weight (g)	240	31.50±0.75 ^a	25.09±0.48 ^b
Yolk length(mm)	240	52.88±0.49 ^a	46.60±0.49 ^b
Yolk height(mm)	240	17.60±0.79	17.39±0.15
Yolk circumference(mm)	240	6.66±0.07 ^a	4.99±0.08 ^b
Yolk Index	240	33.89±0.84 ^a	30.56±0.49 ^b
Albumen weight(g)	240	28.78±0.47 ^b	31.44±0.88 ^a
Albumen height(mm)	240	4.44±0.98 ^b	4.49±0.49 ^a
Albumen Index	240	7.89±0.47 ^a	6.78±0.88 ^b
Haugh Unit	240	73.24±8.44 ^a	71.49±9.48 ^b

^{ab} Means along the same row with different superscripts are significant (P<0.05) different.

chemical analysis of eggs of native fowl, duck and goose. They obtained values that were similar for quality traits such as egg weight, albumin weight, yolk weight, shell weight, shell thickness, albumin index and haugh unit. This current finding was also supported the earlier documentation of Kabir *et al.*, (2013) on their study of egg morphometric analyses in chicken and some selected birds. They revealed similar values that were in accordance with this present result for duck and goose eggs. The external egg quality traits for Duck in the present study was in accordance with the observation of Etuk *et al.*, (2006) who reported similar ranged of values for external egg quality traits for the heaviest duck egg in the semi intensive and intensive management systems. The present observation on the external egg traits was disagreed with the findings of Horbanczuk (2002) and Dariusz *et al.*, (2007). These authors reported a wide range of values higher than this

present result in their studies for Ostrich and pecking duck eggs respectively. Values obtained in this current study for external egg quality trait of Goose were also disagreed with the works of Horbanczuk (2002) and Dariusz *et al.*, (2007). Their observed values for Ostrich and pecking duck eggs were higher than this present finding for Goose eggs. The internal egg quality for Duck in this present study was in harmony with the observations of Nickolova, (2004) and Etuk *et al* (2012). These authors reported a similar range of values for internal egg quality for Muscovy ducks reared under different management systems in the humid tropic of Nigeria which agreed with this present findings. The values obtained for internal egg traits of goose were in agreement with the findings of Mazanowski *et al* (2005). These authors reported a similar range of values of internal egg traits of crossbred geese with Graylag ancestry.

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